

Synthesis and spectroscopic studies on oxovanadium(IV) tetraaza macrocyclic complexes derived from substituted β -diketones and 2,6-diaminopyridine

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Abstract : The *in situ* reactions of 1-phenyl-3-(4-chlorophenyl/4-nitrophenyl/4-methoxyphenyl)-diketone with 2,6-diaminopyridine in the presence of oxovanadium(IV) sulphate yield macrocyclic complexes of type [VO(mac)]SO₄. Attempts to synthesize the corresponding metal free macrocyclic ligands did not prove successful. The magnetic moments of the complexes lie in the range 1.70–1.75 μ_B , suitable for complexes with one unpaired electron. The electronic spectra exhibit three bands. The infrared spectra indicate that the ligands coordinate through four azomethine nitrogen atoms. The fluid solution EPR spectra show an eight line pattern typical for a mononuclear VO^{IV} complexes. The spectral studies support square-pyramidal geometry for the vanadium(IV) complexes.

Keywords : Macrocyclic complexes, oxovanadium(IV), β -diketones.

The intense interest in synthetic macrocycles and their metal complexes depends on the fact that they mimic naturally occurring macrocyclic molecules in their structural and functional features and on their rich chemical behaviour¹⁻⁴. In addition, the study of metal complexes of macrocyclic ligands appears to be interesting in view of the possibility of obtaining coordination compounds of unusual structures and stability. The formation of macrocyclic complexes depends on the size of the macrocycle, on the nature of its donor atoms and on the complexing behaviour of the anions involved in coordination¹. Macrocyclic ligands are also of theoretical interest since they are capable of furnishing an environment of controlled geometry and ligand field strength⁵.

The design and synthesis of polyaza macrocycles have attracted increasing interest in recent years for the possible relevance of these compounds as model, ligands for metal enzymes and metal proteins as metal-ion selective ligands⁶⁻⁹. Synthesis of organic substrates that preferentially interact with particular metal ions is of fundamental importance to many areas of chemistry^{10,11}. Condensation reactions between dicarbonyls and primary diamines have played an important role in the development of synthetic macrocyclic ligands which have been proved to be a fruitful source of imino macrocycle^{1,2}. Usually such synthesis were carried out in the presence of a suitable metal ion which serves to direct the steric course of the reaction preferentially towards cyclic rather than oligo-

meric or polymeric products. Relative to their open-chain analogues, macrocyclic ligands have further stereochemical constraints associated with their cyclic nature, which may influence their potential for metal ion recognition. For macrocycles incorporating rigid or semi-rigid cavities, recognition (and hence discrimination) may be associated with a close match or otherwise of the radius of the metal ion for the cavity^{12,13}.

This paper describes the preparation and characterization of oxovanadium(IV) complexes with macrocyclic ligands derived by the condensation of 2,6-diaminopyridine with substituted β -diketones [1-phenyl-3-(4-chlorophenyl/4-nitrophenyl/4-methoxyphenyl)-diketone].

Experimental

Oxovanadium(IV) was an Aldrich sample and was gravimetrically estimated as vanadate. Estimation of carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen was done at CDRI, Lucknow. Details of physical measurements have been described earlier¹⁴. Substituted β -diketones were prepared by the condensation of acetophenone and different aromatic acid esters by the reported method¹⁵.

Preparation of complexes : To a solution of oxovanadium(IV) sulphate (0.01 mol) in methanol (30 cm³), 2,6-diaminopyridine (0.02 mol) and β -diketone (0.02) dissolved in methanol (30 cm³) were added dropwise with stirring. The mixture was refluxed for ca. 12–20 h

Table 1. Reactions of oxovanadium(IV) sulphate with macrocyclic ligand derived from 2,6-diaminopyridine and β -diketones

Reactants	Molar ratio	Refluxing time (h)	Product, colour, yield (%)	Analysis (%) : Found/(Calcd.)			
				C	H	N	V
$\text{VOSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{DAP} + \text{CDK}$	1 : 2 : 2	12	$[\text{VO}(\text{MDCB})]\text{SO}_4$, dark brown, 60	57.8 (58.0)	3.2 (3.4)	10.0 (10.1)	6.0 (6.2)
$\text{VOSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{DAP} + \text{NDK}$	1 : 2 : 2	20	$[\text{VO}(\text{MDNB})]\text{AO}_4$, greenish brown, 58	56.5 (56.7)	3.2 (3.3)	12.1 (12.2)	5.9 (6.0)
$\text{VOSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{DAP} + \text{MDK}$	1 : 2 : 2	20	$[\text{VO}(\text{MDMB})]\text{SO}_4$, dark brown, 70	61.5 (61.7)	4.0 (4.2)	10.1 (10.3)	6.1 (6.2)

where, DAP = 2,6-diaminopyridine, CDK = 1-phenyl-3-(4-chlorophenyl)-diketone, NDK = 1-phenyl-3-(4-nitrophenyl)-diketone, MDK = 1-phenyl-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-diketone, MDCB = macrocyclic ligand derived from 2,6-diaminopyridine and CDK, MDNB = macrocyclic ligand derived from 2,6-diaminopyridine and NDK, MDMB = macrocyclic ligand derived from 2,6-diaminopyridine and MDK.

when dark brown coloured precipitate was obtained. The product was filtered off, washed with hot methanol and dried *in vacuo*. The product was identified to be a macrocyclic complex $[\text{VO}(\text{mac})]\text{SO}_4$. Yield : 58-70%.

The details of the reactions and analytical data of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Results and discussion

The reactions of 2,6-diaminopyridine with β -diketones in 1 : 1 molar ratio, respectively, using oxovanadium(IV) as template agent gave the macrocyclic complexes of stoichiometry $[\text{VO}(\text{mac})]\text{SO}_4$ (1), where (mac) is the macrocyclic ligand derived from condensation of 2,6-diaminopyridine with substituted β -diketones, according to Scheme 1.

X = -Cl (MDCB), -NO₂ (MDNB), -OCH₃ (MDMB)

Scheme 1. Synthetic route for macrocyclic complexes of oxovanadium(IV).

The elemental analyses for these complexes are given in Table 1. The macrocyclic complexes are soluble in dimethylformamide, dimethylsulphoxide and nitrobenzene. Molar conductance measurements in dimethylformamide show that these complexes are electrolytic in nature.

Magnetic moment and electronic spectra : The room temperature magnetic moments of the oxovanadium(IV) complexes lie in the range 1.70–1.75 μ_B , corresponding to one unpaired electron. These values are well within the range reported¹⁶ for monomeric oxovanadium(IV) complexes.

The electronic spectra of the oxovanadium(IV) complexes having a square pyramidal or a distorted octahedral structure are most often interpreted in terms of energy level scheme proposed¹⁷ by Ballhausen and Gray. Usually, three optical bands are observed in the visible region, assigned to ${}^2B_2(d_{xy}) \rightarrow {}^2E(d_{xz}, d_{yz})$ (ν_1), ${}^2B_2(d_{xy}) \rightarrow {}^2B_1(d_{x^2-y^2})$ (ν_2) and ${}^2B_2(d_{xy}) \rightarrow {}^2A_1(d_{z^2})$ (ν_3). The ν_3 band is often obscured by intense charge-transfer absorptions. The nujol mull spectra of the complexes (Table 2), reported in this section, exhibit two bands at *ca.* 12000–13500 cm^{-1} (ν_1) and 18500–19200 cm^{-1} (ν_2) and at *ca.* 30000 cm^{-1} is probably due to a oxo \rightarrow vanadium(IV) charge-transfer admixed with $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$ (ν_3) transition.

Infrared spectra : The infrared spectra of the complexes $[\text{VO}(\text{L})]\text{SO}_4$ do not show any band characteristics of free carbonyl group (i.e. near 1670 cm^{-1}). Instead, all the complexes exhibit, a single sharp absorption band in the 1600–1615 cm^{-1} region, assignable to coordinated $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ vibration. This also suggests the Schiff base condensation¹⁸⁻²⁰ between β -diketone and 2,6-diaminopyridine. This also confirms that the proposed ligand framework is formed. This has been further corroborated by the appearance of a sharp band in the 360–340 cm^{-1} region, which may reasonably be assigned¹⁶ to

Table 2. Magnetic moments and electronic spectral bands of oxovanadium(IV) complexes with tetraaza macrocyclic ligands derived from 2,6-diaminopyridine and substituted β -diketones

Complex	μ_{eff} (300 K)	Electronic spectral bands (cm^{-1})		
		${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$	${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$	${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1 +$ charge-transfer
[VO(MDCB)]SO ₄	1.75	13500	18600	29800
[VO(MDNB)]SO ₄	1.70	12800	18500	30000
[VO(MDMB)]SO ₄	1.72	12000	19200	29600

Table 3. ESR parameters of oxovanadium(IV) complexes with macrocyclic ligands derived from 2,6-diaminopyridine and substituted β -diketones

Complex	g_{av}	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	A_{av}	A_{\parallel} $\times 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	A_{\perp}
[VO(MDCB)]SO ₄	1.971	1.958	1.997	86.5	135	62.2
[VO(MDNB)]SO ₄	1.978	1.946	1.994	91.0	138	67.5
[VO(MDMB)]SO ₄	1.980	1.950	1.981	88.0	134	65.0

$\nu(\text{V}-\text{N})$. Pyridine ring deformation bands appear at *ca.* 1580, 670 and 400 cm^{-1} . These bands appear almost at the same frequencies as in 2,6-diaminopyridine showing that pyridine nitrogen is not involved in coordination²⁰. A large number of bands also arise due to phenyl ring and different alkyl groups but definite assignments of these bands are not possible due to the complexity of the spectrum arising out of the overlap of these absorptions.

The spectra of all oxovanadium(IV) complexes show new bands at *ca.* 940–950 cm^{-1} which are assigned to $\nu(\text{V}=\text{O})$ vibration. This frequency is at the low end of the range 930–1040 cm^{-1} , reported for a large set of oxovanadium complexes. It has been reported²¹ that the $\text{V}=\text{O}$ stretching frequency is susceptible to a number of influences including electron donation from basal plane ligand atoms, solid state effects and the nature of anion. It has been mentioned that electron withdrawing groups attached to ligands, cause a lowering of the $\nu(\text{V}=\text{O})$ frequency and vice versa. The lowest $\nu(\text{V}=\text{O})$ frequency has been observed with complex derived from 1-phenyl-3-(4-chlorophenyl)-diketone which further confirms this fact.

The presence of an ionic sulphate group has been confirmed²² by appearance of three bands at *ca.* 1140 (ν_3), 900 (ν_1) and 610 cm^{-1} (ν_4). The absence of a ν_2 band and non-splitting of ν_3 band indicate that Td symmetry is still held.

Thus, the infrared spectral data show that the ligands act as N₄ chelating agents, bonded with all the four azomethine nitrogen atoms to the oxovanadium(IV) ion.

Electron spin resonance spectra : In the solid state,

the ESR spectra of complexes show a single line feature $g \approx 1.97$. The fluid solution (DMSO) spectra at room temperature show an eight line pattern, typical of mononuclear oxovanadium(IV) complexes (${}^51\text{V}$; $I = 7/2$) with $g_{\text{iso}} \approx 1.975$ and $A_{\text{iso}} \approx 0.008 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. At the liquid nitrogen temperature, the spectra display well resolved axial anisotropy with two sets of eight-line pattern. The g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} , A_{\parallel} and A_{\perp} values were evaluated and the values, thus obtained, are tabulated in Table 3. The values are typical of the spectra displayed by square-pyramidal oxovanadium(IV) complexes with unpaired electron in an orbital of mostly d_{xy} character (ligand along x and y axes). Inspection of these data reveals a close agreement between the spectral parameters obtained at room temperature and at the liquid nitrogen temperature, indicating the complexes retaining their structural identity throughout this temperature range.

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References

1. L. F. Lindoy, "The Chemistry of Macrocyclic Ligand Complexes", Cambridge University Press, UK, 1989.
2. P. Dietrich, P. Viout and J. M. Lehn, "Macrocyclic Chemistry", VCH Publishers Inc., New York, 1993.
3. R. M. Izatt, K. Powlak and J. S. Bradshaw, *Chem. Rev.*, 1991, **91**, 1721.
4. F. Lions, *Rev. Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1969, **19**, 177.
5. G. A. Melson, "Coordination Chemistry of Macrocyclic Com-

- pounds". Plenum Press, New York, 1979.
- M. Mitewa and P. R. Bontchev, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1994, **135**, 129.
 - B. Dietrich, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1993, **65**, 1457.
 - C. Steel, A. Galan and J. de Mendoza, *Top. Curr. Chem.*, 1995, **175**, 101.
 - G. Ricciardi, A. Bavoso, A. Bencini, A. Rosa, F. Lelj and F. Bonosi, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1996, 2799.
 - M. M. Jones, "Ligand Reactivity and Catalysis", Academic Press, New York, 1968.
 - D. H. Bush, "Reactions of Coordinated Ligands and Homogeneous Catalysis", ACS Symposium Series, 1963, 37.
 - E. C. Constable and J. Lewis, *Polyhedron*, 1982, **1**, 303.
 - E. C. Constable and J. M. Holmes, *Polyhedron*, 1988, **7**, 2531.
 - S. K. Sengupta, O. P. Pandey, J. K. Pandey and G. K. Pandey, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2002, **55**, 1455.
 - V. K. Singh, PhD Thesis. DDU Gorakhpur University, 1976.
 - S. Yadav, O. P. Pandey and S. K. Sengupta, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1995, **20**, 107.
 - C. J. Ballhausen and H. B. Gray, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 111.
 - H. D. S. Yadav, S. K. Sengupta and S. C. Tripathi, *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1985, 1180.
 - H. D. S. Yadav, S. K. Sengupta and S. C. Tripathi, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1984, **14**, 867.
 - U. K. Pandey, O. P. Pandey, S. K. Sengupta and S. C. Tripathi, *Polyhedron*, 1987, **6**, 1611.
 - O. P. Pandey, *Polyhedron*, 1986, **5**, 1587.
 - S. K. Sengupta, O. P. Pandey, J. K. Pandey and G. K. Pandey, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 887.